

LUS THERAPY IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS

Pulatov Ulugbek Sunatovich¹

Hamdullaev Mehroj Sirojiddinovich²

¹ Associate Professor, Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand,
Uzbekistan ² Ordinator, Samarkand state medical university,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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Anatation: This article presents the results of the use of low-frequency ultrasound therapy in pregnant women with chronic rhinosinusitis in remission. The aim of the study was to study the effects of low-frequency ultrasound therapy and to substantiate the feasibility of this procedure as an alternative to antibiotic therapy. The study was conducted in the ENT department¹ of the SamMI clinic. 30 pregnant women were studied for the autumn period of 2021.

Key words: chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS), low-frequency ultrasound (LUS) therapy, pregnancy, antibiotic therapy, remission period, phonophoresis.

Introduction. Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is one of the most common diseases in outpatient and inpatient practice, affecting all age groups at the same frequency. The steady increase in the incidence of SRS, leading to significant complications of its progradient orientation, suggests that this is a condition of not only medical but also social significance [3,10].

According to a study by Ovchinnikov A.Yu (2020), the EPOS 2020 report shows that 18-20% of all primary care visits fall on confirmed (18%) or suspected (1-2%) cases of rhinosinusitis. However, according to the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, more than 2.8 million people in the U.S. suffer from antibiotic-resistant infections each year, leading to more than 35,000 deaths [7]. Djabbarova D.R. (2018) reported that 5–15% of adults and 5% of children were infected with various rhinosinusitis. In recent years, the disease has been growing in the number of pregnant women [2].

Of course, effective treatment of this disease, especially the prolongation of the remission period of the chronic form, is very important. As with all inflammatory diseases, standard antibiotics are used to treat this disease, but these treatments have been shown to lead to antibiotic resistance in patients with chronic RS. In particular, the treatment of SRS in pregnant women is still controversial. Some studies recommend the use of natural remedies in addition to treatment tactics [1,3,7].

In recent years, physiotherapeutic methods have been improving and taking their place. Low-frequency ultrasound therapy is now widely used [11]. However, their use in pregnant women has not yet been fully elucidated.

Materials and methods. During the study, 30 pregnant women aged 19 to 35 years were medically examined and treated in the otolaryngology department of SamMU Clinic No. 1. The duration of the disease ranged from 1 to 3 years. 10 patients were hospitalized, 20 patients received outpatient care.

The control group included 30 pregnant women diagnosed with SRS who were prescribed standard treatment. The presence of SRS was confirmed by anamnestic data, results of otolaryngological examination, bacteriological examination of pathological discharge from the nasal sinuses and nasal cavity, results of assessment of respiratory and olfactory activity, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the nasal sinuses.

Pregnant women in the main group received an antibacterial drug after cleansing of the nasal mucosa and sinuses, after initial anesthesia, and in endonasal injection against the background of oral administration of LUS and 2nd generation antihistamines during remission. After initial cleansing and rinsing of the nasal cavity during remission, local drug flumarin nasal spray 22 mg / ml and phonophoresis with novacaine on the background of LUS were prescribed.

The control group received the antibacterial drug parenterally (cefamed at a dose of 1 g 1 time per day) after daily anesthesia of the nasal mucosa, as well as 2nd generation antihistamines were prescribed.

Results. The results of the study showed that rhinosinusitis was chronic in all women, with an average disease duration of 1.7 ± 0.68 years. Patients complained of general weakness, nasal discharge, and difficulty breathing. 80% of pregnant women only restored airway patency by rinsing their noses, while the rest used local vasoconstrictor sprays. Figure 1 shows an analysis of pregnant complaints.

Figure 1. Analysis of complaints from the main group of patients in the study

According to the analysis of the anamnesis, 50% of patients in the main group reported the presence of allergic diseases, and in the control group this indicator was not significantly different (46.7%). During the year, the incidence of acute respiratory diseases and influenza averaged 3 ± 0.4 times. This indicator may also be associated with weakened immune systems during pregnancy.

Anemia was detected in the majority of patients (66.7%) during the mining analysis, of which moderate was detected in 30% and mild in 70%. Leukocyte changes were noted in 83.3%, of which leukocytosis was significant in 50%. There was an increase in lymphocytes and a decrease in total protein.

Of the patients treated in the main group, 28 (93.3%) pregnant women reported a positive result, while in the control group this figure was 83.3%. The average duration of treatment was 5.03 ± 0.54 days in the main group and 6.12 ± 1.02 days in the control group. The duration of the remission period was longer in the main group of patients following the recommendations given.

Conclusion. Thus, a comparative analysis demonstrated the safety and efficacy of local antibiotic therapy and phonophoresis of novacaine in combination with LUS, as well as its superiority over parenteral and topical use of antibacterial drugs in the treatment of SRS.

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